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DOI: [https://doi.org/10.33272/2522-9729-2021-2\(197\)-12-17](https://doi.org/10.33272/2522-9729-2021-2(197)-12-17)**Vovk Myroslava****Hryshchenko Yuliia**ORCID iD <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-9109-9194>ORCID iD <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-9822-9668>

SCIENTIFIC AND PEDAGOGICAL SCHOOLS PROMOTION WITHIN THE HUMANISTIC VALUES DEVELOPMENT

- S** *In terms of globalization Ukrainian education, reflecting the research achievements of pedagogical thought and practice has a strong potential towards intellectual, axiological and cultural, aesthetic, moral and ethical development of the person. Ethical and cultural values of education should be extrapolated in the European environment to promote multiculturalism, anthropocentrism, humanistic principles, as well as the culturological and Europe-oriented paradigm in the educational sphere of Ukraine.*

The leading trend in the development of Ukrainian and world pedagogical science is fundamentalisation, which is the basis of the «advance» education in the context of sustainable development of society. The primary principles of education in its interdisciplinary measurement were established through the activities of the university and academic centres where scientific schools were formed in retrospect. According to this, the elaboration of methodological, theoretical, and practice-oriented achievements of scientific schools in the pedagogical and educational environment occurs through the continuity of generations of scientists, the actualization of achievements of experienced scientists, and their combination with the innovations of young scientists. The synthesis of these two layers of science allows solving present issues that arise in modern educational science and practice. There is the need to globalize the experience of development of scientific schools in the modern education and educational environment of Ukraine, particularly in academic centres, that represents the development of educational science in the personalized dimension and confirms the crystallization of its fundamental principles and innovative nature of scientific research.

We summarised the achievements of the leading academic institution of Ukraine – Ivan Ziaziun Institute of Pedagogical Education and Adult Education of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine – in the personalized context and outlined the prospects for the development of scientific schools of the Institute to meet modern challenges of reforming education and science.

We described the trends in the development of scientific schools of the well-known Ukrainian scientists and educators (I. Ziaziun, S. Honcharenko, N. Hychkalo, L. Lukianova, L. Khomych), which were formed on the values of pedagogical mentoring, intellectual leadership, empathy, ethical and aesthetic philosophical guidelines.

Key words: scientific school; scientific and pedagogical school; academic centre; Ivan Ziaziun Institute of Pedagogical Education and Adult Education; the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine

- A** **Мирослава Вовк, Грищенко Юлія. Розвиток науково-педагогічних шкіл у контексті утвердження гуманістичних цінностей.**

В умовах глобалізаційних процесів українська освіта, акумулювавши досягнення педагогічної наукової думки і практики, має потужний потенціал у напрямі інтелектуального, аксіокультурного, естетичного, морально-етичного розвитку особистості. Етнокультурні цінності освіти мають екстраполюватись у європейське середовище з метою утвердження полікультурності, людиноцентризму, гуманістичних принципів, культурологічної та європейсько зорієнтованої парадигми в освітньому просторі України.

Провідною тенденцією розвитку української й світової педагогічної науки є фундаменталізація, що становить підґрунтя «випереджувальної» освіти у контексті забезпечення сталого розвитку суспільства. Фундаментальні засади педагогіки у її інтердисциплінарному вимірі утверджувалися через діяльність університетських та академічних осередків, у яких в історичній ретроспективі формувалися наукові школи. Відповідно кристалізація методологічних, теоретичних, практико орієнтованих досягнень наукових шкіл у педагогічно-освітнянському середовищі відбувається шляхом збереження наступності поколінь науковців, актуалізації надбань досвідчених учених та їх поєднання з інноваціями молодих науковців. Синтез цих двох пластів науки дає змогу вирішувати актуальні проблеми, що виникають у сучасній педагогічній науці й освітній практиці.

Виникає потреба узагальнення досвіду розвитку наукових шкіл у сучасному освітянсько-педагогічному середовищі України, зокрема в академічних осередках, що репрезентує розвиток педагогічної науки у персонологічному вимірі та підтверджує кристалізацію її фундаментальних засад та інноваційну спрямованість наукового пошуку.

Узагальноно здобутки провідної академічної установи України – Інституту педагогічної освіти і освіти дорослих НАПН України імені Івана Зязюна – у персонологічному контексті та окреслено перспективи розвитку наукових шкіл інституту з урахуванням сучасних викликів реформування освіти і науки.

Охарактеризовано напрями розвитку наукових шкіл відомих українських науковців-освітян (І. Зязюна, С. Гончаренка, Н. Ничкало, Л. Лук'янової, Л. Хомич), що сформувались на цінностях педагогічного наставництва, інтелектуального лідерства, емпатійності та етико-естетичних світоглядних орієнтирів.

Ключові слова: наукова школа; науково-педагогічна школа; академічний осередок; Інститут педагогічної освіти і освіти дорослих імені Івана Зязюна; Національна академія педагогічних наук України

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The urgency of the problem. In terms of globalization the Ukrainian education, reflecting the research achievements of pedagogical thought and practice, has a strong potential towards intellectual, axiological and cultural, aesthetic, moral and ethical development of the person. Ethical and cultural values of education should be extrapolated in the European environment in order to promote multiculturalism, anthropocentrism, humanistic principles, as well as the culturological and Europe-oriented paradigm in the educational sphere of Ukraine.

The leading trend in the development of Ukrainian and world pedagogical science is fundamentalisation, which is the basis of the «advance» education in the context of sustainable development of society. The primary principles of pedagogy in its interdisciplinary measurement were established through the activities of the university and academic centres where scientific schools were formed in retrospect. According to this, the elaboration of methodological, theoretical, and practice-oriented achievements of scientific schools in the pedagogical and educational environment occurs through the continuity of generations of scientists, the actualization of achievements of experienced scientists, and their combination with the innovations of young scientists. The synthesis of these two layers of science allows solving present issues that arise in modern pedagogical science and educational practice. In this context, there is the sonorous idea of V. Andrushchenko, who noted that «the scientific result ripens through the cooperation of several generations of scientists who «stand on the shoulders» of each other and, continuing the research of their predecessors, give to young scientists the inherited and personal achievements» [1, p. 5-7].

Analysis of previous research and publications. In the modern pedagogical discourse, the phenomenon of scientific schools is considered by Ukrainian and foreign scientists from the point of methodological guidelines (S. Honcharenko, A. Dubaseniuk, D. Zerbino, L. Landau, O. Oleksiuk, etc.), pedagogical per-

sonology (I. Kovchyna, M. Leshchenko, N. Nychkalo, A. Semenoh, etc.), historical and pedagogical analysis (A. Hnizdilova, N. Demianenko, etc.). At the same time, there is a need of generalisation of experience in the development of scientific schools in the educational and pedagogical environment of Ukraine, particularly in academic centres, representing the development of pedagogical science in the personological dimension and confirming the crystallisation of its fundamental principles and innovative nature of scientific research.

Selection of previously unsolved parts of the general problem to which this article is devoted. The study of prospects for the development of scientific schools of the Institute of Pedagogical Education and Adult Education of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine are connected with the needs of society with respect to ensuring lifelong education of various categories of adults, implementation of innovations, provision of the relation between science and educational practice, preservation of national achievements of pedagogical scientific thinking, promotion of the integration of the educational community in the international scientific and educational environment, support of scientific mentorship as an important factor in creating a young generation of scientists and educators.

Formulation of the goals of the article (task statement) is to summarise the achievements of the leading academic institution of Ukraine – the Institute of Pedagogical and Adult Education of the NAES of Ukraine – in the context of personology and definition of prospects for the development of scientific schools of the Institute to meet modern challenges of reforming education and science.

Presentation of the main material of the study. Summarising the ideas of scholars regarding the determination of essence of concept «scientific school», we should note that there is a certain ambiguity in its interpretation. K. Lange noted that «scientific school is an informal research team formed by a prominent

scientist on the basis of the classic university or research institution for the purpose of collective development of a certain scientific idea (issue, trend)» [4, с. 207]. B. Kedrov considers scientific school as «a structural branch of modern science, which allows to concentrate the efforts of a large group of relatively young scientists under the direct supervision of the founder of this scientific direction on dealing with a specific, limited range of pressing issues in a particular field of science» [11, p. 309]. By the definition of D. Zerbino, «scientific school is a professional voluntary community of people, formed under the auspices of the personality of the scholar-leader. It is engaged in active research work in the new topical direction and united by the ideas, methods, scientific tradition, and collaboration that expand the search for new facts» [3, p. 10]. Accordingly, we shall note that the scientific school in pedagogy is developing under the auspices of a scientist-mentor, whose personal mentoring talent, production of scientific ideas that are innovative for a certain period of time, on the grounds of ethical values and accurate ideology-oriented position, guides young researchers to the development of a certain direction in the pedagogical science, the formation of subdisciplines in pedagogy, the support of their theoretical and methodological fundamentals, the establishment of practice-oriented results that should be based on scientific and educational traditions and take into account innovative changes in the pedagogical environment.

Over the years, several scientific schools were formed in the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine: psychological school of Academician of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine, Director of G. Kostyuk Institute of Psychology S. Maksimenko; scientific and pedagogical school of Academician of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine, Academician-Secretary of the Department of Higher Education M. Evtukh; psychological and pedagogical school of Academician of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine, Director of the Institute of Educational Issues I. Bekh; and scientific school of Academician of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine, Chief Researcher of the Institute of Pedagogy O. Savchenko, etc.

Established in 1996, the Institute of Pedagogical and Adult Education of the National Academy of Pedagogical Science of Ukraine is a powerful centre for the development of scientific schools. During the nearly 20-year period of activity of the institution, there were formed several generations of researchers that were developing their scientific and research potential, receiving degrees of candidate, doctor of pedagogical or psychological sciences, and establishing their own scientific schools.

M. Leshchenko convincingly proves the role of the leader of the scientific school and focuses on the personological aspect of its development. The scientist says that the research work of young scholars «should be concentrated in the field of ideas, created by a scientist of high spiritual and intellectual potential. Moreover, the prerequisite for the establishment of any scientific school is the presence of spiritually and intellectually talented scientist – the founder of the school» [5, с. 259-269]. Among the talented founders of scientific schools in the Institute whose own professional activity and life philosophy manifest intellectualism

and anthropocentrism in the pedagogical science, we shall name the founders and representatives of the Institute of different periods: S. Honcharenko, I. Ziaziun, N. Nychkalo, A. Rudnytska, V. Rybalka, L. Lukianova, L. Khomych, O. Lavrinenko, O. Kucheriavy, A. Semenoh, and others.

The scientific school of the Doctor of Philosophical Sciences, Professor, Academician, long-term Director of the Institute Ivan Ziaziun was developing in the context of adopting philosophical and axiological priorities of pedagogical education, theoretical fundamentals for the development of the pedagogical skill of a teacher. Exploring the scientific and pedagogical heritage of I. Ziaziun, Academician N. Nychkalo noted that «his scientific school has trained thousands of qualified teachers and researchers for different regions of Ukraine, Poland, Russia, and other countries who work productively at the expanse of pedagogical science and practice, make a significant contribution to the development of professional education, embodying Beauty, Goodness, and Truth in teaching activities and scientific research» [6, p. 21]. The scientific school of I. Ziaziun covers various areas of pedagogical education. Under the mentorship of Ivan Ziaziun, twenty doctoral and nineteen candidate's dissertations in the field of pedagogy and psychology of professional education were defended.

The role of art in professional training of a teacher was investigated in dissertations of M. Bukach, V. Orlov, O. Otych, V. Rashkovska, T. Smyrnov, etc. Students of I. Ziaziun have achieved significant results in their scientific research, containing studies that make actual the ideas of outstanding Ukrainian teachers and scientists (S. Karpenchuk, E. Bilichenko, A. Leshchenko, etc.). The foreign experience of pedagogical education is the current direction of his scientific school that has become the subject of research for such scholars as T. Koshmanov, M. Leshchenko. The historical genesis of professional education in Ukraine under the guidance of the talented mentor was studied by M. Neshchadym, Z. Hipters, N. Filipchuk. The problems of aesthetics and ethics of pedagogical influence were formulated by I. Androshchuk, I. Zaitseva, T. Skoryk, A. Shevniuk, etc.

M. Leshchenko notes that the guiding principle of the scientific school of Academician I. Ziaziun is the integrity of the study of pedagogical skill of a teacher that «is formed through the application of some principles of scientific research, namely: the unity of science and art; the knowledge of human nature; the personification of educational process (relation between teachers and students on the basis of cognitive activities and personal meanings of being); the metacognitive determination of scientific research (critical analysis and reinterpretation of the results obtained in the context of development of personal philosophical positions)» [5, p. 263]. The conceptual ideas of the scientific school of I. Ziaziun are based on ethical and aesthetic guidelines of the pedagogical influence of a teacher and master, philosophical principles of the «Pedagogy of Kindness», and culture-centrism in the content of modern education.

The scientific school of Academician Semen Honcharenko is fundamental in the modern pedagogical discourse and perspective in the scope of innovative processes of education. The mentor, exploring the phenomenon of scientific schools of peda-

gogy, noted that «one of the most important laws of science is the strict continuity of ideas, concepts, and methods of research, which constitute the content of any science. People of different generations, carrying out the process of scientific development, seem to pass their accumulated «spiritual capital from hand to hand. In this regard, there is a well-known perennial problem of teachers and students, older and younger generations in science, the founders of new scientific trends and their successors – the problem of scientific schools» [2, p. 27-43].

Starting a scientific career at the Institute of Pedagogy of the Ukrainian SSR (now – the Institute of Pedagogy of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine) and continuing it in the Institute of Pedagogy and Psychology of Professional Education of the Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine (now – the Institute of Professional and Adult Education of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine), Semen Honcharenko became Director and Consultant of scientific works, including 30 doctor's and 55 master's dissertations.

Scientific research under the guidance of S. Honcharenko covered a range of problematic areas: methodology of pedagogy, various aspects of humanization, humanitarianization of education, fundamentalization of secondary and higher education, scientific support for pedagogical research. Among the representatives of the scientific school of Semen Honcharenko, there are scientists and educators who are well-known in Ukraine and abroad: R. Hurevych, L. Lukianova, O. Romanovsky, H. Filipchuk, etc.

Employees, doctoral students and postgraduates of the Institute of Pedagogical and Adult Education of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine considered a piece of advice and valuable recommendation of Semen Honcharenko to be an honour, as he was the outstanding scientist, methodologist, didactic, as well as the ordinary wise and sincere person. The talent of pedagogical mentoring, the skill of pedagogical tact and culture, «humanization» of the pedagogical influence became powerful instruments of the intellectual, emotional, aesthetic, and ethical impact on young scientists.

The contribution of Semen Honcharenko and his followers to the development of interdisciplinary pedagogy, formation of the theory and the practice of its subdisciplines is invaluable. In this regard, N. Nychkalo noted that «the justification of provisions in pedagogy, as a particular field of social practice, and a proper, functioning in its depths, industry of knowledge production – this conclusion of Academician S. Honcharenko has methodological significance for the development of pedagogical science» [6].

The Ukrainian scientific school of theory of art education was formed under the guidance of Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor Oksana Rudnytska. O. Oleksiuk rightly noted that «the results of the research of issues in the philosophy of art education, obtained by O. Rudnytska and her followers, are invaluable, because her scientific school is a unique phenomenon in the development of art education in Ukraine» [8, p. 40].

The qualities of a leader of the scientific school of O. Rudnytska were detected not only in her profound philosophical thinking, scientific talent, and high level of professionalism as a musician

but also in her skills as a teacher and mentor, which involved primarily interpersonal professional communication. After all, O. Rudnytska was convinced that «the dialogic communication, as a complex and multifaceted process, covers the interaction of individuals, the exchange of information between them, the emergence and adoption of a position that is close to both parties, the expression of the attitude to each other, the inter-influence and the mutual understanding, the ability to have this type of relations, the perception of the uniqueness of a partner and allowing him/her to be himself/herself, characterizes the quality of communication» [9, p. 63].

The scientific school of Professor O. Rudnytska developed rapidly and became fairly well-known among the scholars of Ukraine and abroad. Her followers carried out research in the field of art education, particularly, on the use of music in personal development and professional skills of a future teacher, the study of the impact of music perception on the formation of professionally significant qualities of a future teacher, relative to the historical retrospective of the development of art education in Ukraine and its regions.

O. Rudnytska was the first one in the Ukrainian pedagogical science who substantiated the theoretical and methodological fundamentals of art education as an independent branch of professional education; determined its development priorities in the changing educational paradigm and socio-cultural dynamics of XXI century; identified the influence of art on the formation of personality in the context of modernization and globalization of cultural and educational processes in the world [9, p. 4].

Under the mentorship of O. Rudnytska, a number of doctor's and master's dissertations were defended, including: on the training of teachers (L. Khomych, P. Kharchenko, Z. Syrota), on the formation of pedagogical skill of future teachers of music by means of art (T. Stratan), on the formation of professional culture of future teachers of fine art (M. Pichkur), on the history of the development of art education in Ukraine (O. Tsvygun, O. Popyk, Yu. Hryshchenko), on the formation of philosophical culture and moral education of future teachers by means of art (V. Smikal, L. Moskaliova), etc. The ideas of O. Rudnytska concerning the conceptual fundamentals for the development of art education, the priorities of the new pedagogical thinking (humanism, cultural responsibility, spirituality, symbolism, multiculturalism, etc.), national historical traditions, and enshrining the principles of innovation gained new scientific understanding in the context of the reform of modern creative scientific and educational fields.

At the present stage, under the auspices of the Institute of Pedagogical and Adult Education of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine, there is the active development of scientific schools of talented teachers, whose activity is aimed at the preservation of fundamentality of the modern pedagogical science, strengthening its interdisciplinary character and adaptation of modern innovation processes in the pro-European vector of development.

The founder of the scientific school is Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor, Member of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine, Academician-Secretary of the Department of Professional and Adult Education of the National

Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine Nelliya Nychkalo. Among authoritative representatives of the Ukrainian and European pedagogical community, Nelliya Nychkalo is characterized by the special attention to the issues of the philosophy of education, professional pedagogy, theory and practice of lifelong education, comparative pedagogy, pedagogy of work, training, psychology and didactics of professional education, psychology of professional development of an individual. Analyzing key concepts of self-concept of Academician N. Nychkalo, O. Semenoh notes that Nelliya Nychkalo – «a talented scientist of the European scale, whose professional activity is based on a solid foundation of system thinking, strategic vision and titanic work» [10, p. 9-20].

Upholding the principles anthropocentrism, sincerity, dedication to one's work, exactingness to oneself and others, and always supporting talented young researchers, Nelliya Hryhorivna has created a powerful scientific school that is known not only in Ukraine but also abroad. Under the guidance of Nelliya Nychkalo, more than 30 doctor's and 80 master's dissertations were defended. The research work of students of Nelliya Nychkalo was devoted to the issues of comparative pedagogy (N. Abashkina, N. Bidiuk, T. Desiatov, O. Ohienko), theory and history of pedagogical science and educational practice in Ukraine (O. Anishchenko, I. Kurliak, I. Likarchuk, T. Usatenko), theoretical and methodological fundamentals of professional education (O. Dubaseniuk, V. Radkevych, F. Shliosek), humanization and humanitarianization of higher education (I. Kuznetsova, L. Babenko, H. Voronka, S. Romanova), etc. Nelliya Nychkalo is a generator of innovative ideas in the development of subdisciplines in pedagogy, inspirational mentor of those interested in modern issues of pedagogical theory and educational practice of scientists, educators shaping a new generation of scientific and pedagogical elite of Ukraine considering the European principles of education and science: tolerance, intercultural communication, open dialogue, and academic mobility.

In the modern scientific and educational environment of Ukraine, there is the active development of the scientific school of Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor, Corresponding Member of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine, Director of the Institute of Pedagogical and Adult Education of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine Larysa Lukianova. Under her guidance, 8 doctor's and 11 candidate's dissertations on the theory and methods of professional education were defended.

The conceptual bases of professional activity of L. Lukianova differs with innovative ideas, modern European vision of professional education, adult education, and lifelong education. She is one of the founders of the theory of adult education in Ukraine. Professor L. Lukianova is the author of more than 250 scientific and methodological works, as well as the concept of adult education in Ukraine, which received support and was approved by the Presidium of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine.

As a leader of the scientific school and Director of the Institute of Pedagogical and Adult Education of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine, Larysa Lukianova has such personal and professional qualities that allow her to successfully

lead the research team and their students (graduate and doctoral students). Having qualities of a real leader who knows how to organize scientific work, help, and advise, L. Lukianova contributes to the personal development of every student: initiates training, scientific platforms, seminars, international cooperation, and the like.

Issues of scientific research of students of L. Lukianova are quite various: comparative study of the systems of adult education in the international dimension (S. Babushko, N. Demeshkant, O. Zhyzhko, E. Bohiv, I. Sahun); preparing and raising the qualification of a teacher of professional training (H. Krasylnikova, N. Samoiloiva); theoretical and methodological fundamentals of adult education (O. Voliarska, I. Herasimova); formation of ecological competence of future specialists (A. Hurenkova, N. Nehrutsa), etc.

The scientific school of L. Lukianova is developing on the basis of the principles of scientific character, integrity, tenacity, intelligence, predictability, humanity, the value of person's ascent to the heights of scientific success. Focusing on the European vector in the development of pedagogical science, Larysa Lukianova supports the activities of the UNESCO Department «Lifelong Professional Education in XXI Century». She has initiated the establishment of the Council of Young Scientists of the Institute of Pedagogical and Adult Education of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine.

In the framework of activities of the Institute, there is the fundamental development of the scientific school on problems of psychological and pedagogical training of teachers formed by Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor, Deputy Director of scientific work Lidia Khomych. Having passed the way from a teacher of the Kyiv secondary school to Deputy Director, L. Khomych created her own scientific school. Under her guidance, 5 doctor's (H. Voskoboynikov, O. Fedy, T. Yatsula, O. Lavrentiev, H. Matukova) and more than 20 candidate's dissertations were defended. The scientific search of her students is aimed at updating the content, methods, forms, technologies of pedagogical education, professional training for teachers in higher educational institutions in the context of the axiological paradigm of modern education.

Conclusions from this study. Consequently, scientific schools in the Institute of Pedagogical and Adult Education of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine developed on the basis of fundamental scientific traditions and innovative vector in the development of pedagogical science and education in the European dimension. The activities of scientific schools in the leading academic centre of Ukraine confirms the implementation of such priorities in the national scientific and educational environment as: constant generation of new ideas, development of the tradition of true scientific thinking, maintaining the spirit of partnership, intercultural communication, scientific dialogue, discussions, formation the ability of young researchers to bold initiative and to self-criticism, establishment of humanistic principles of science with the aim of forming a new type of a future specialist as a person of culture, of new generation with the former national innovation-conscious and tolerant international ideological position.

Prospects for further exploration. Further scientific research should be aimed at studying the genesis of leading scientific and pedagogical schools, which are fundamental and innovative centers in the system of pedagogical education and adult education. These centers were formed primarily in the academic institutions of the National Academy Sciences of Ukraine, industry academies and universities.

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